

Gaia chromaticity calibration and the BBP filter shape

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ABSTRACT. The criticality of the BBP filter slopes for the chromaticity calibration is studied for trapezoidal transmittance curves. The chromaticity prediction error is calculated for stellar and quasar spectra, using a linear calibration model fitted to the BBP fluxes of normal stars. The edge width has little impact on the prediction error as long as the edge width is much less than the filter bandwidth. The impact on the final astrometric accuracy is in any case small for stars with normal spectra; worse (but probably still acceptable) for objects with emission-line spectra such as quasars. The prediction error appears to ‘explode’ when the RMS WFE approaches 50 nm.

1 Introduction

An action to study the astrophysical criticality of the filter slopes in the Gaia photometric systems was defined in GAIA-CUO-124. The present note concerns the filter shape of the broad-band photometer (BBP) from the viewpoint of chromaticity correction.

Previous studies of the chromaticity calibration (mainly in GAIA-LL-039 and a subsequent attempt to optimise the BBP passbands by means of a neural network) gave a strong preference for triangular or bell-shaped, widely overlapping passbands. But while these were definitely found to be superior to more rectangular-shaped passbands, it was not clear whether the chromaticity correction actually required such unorthodox passbands for the BBP. The aim of this note is to answer that question.

For an assumed BBP filter system, the prediction error on the chromaticity is evaluated for stellar and quasar spectra after calibration with the simplest possible (linear) model. The RMS prediction error for normal stellar spectra is relevant for the limiting accuracy of bright stars, while the (larger) RMS error for quasar spectra is relevant for the stability of the extragalactic reference frame and for the limitations caused by strongly peculiar (emission-line) spectra.

The assumed symmetric trapezoidal filters are parameterized by the central wavelength (λ_0), bandwidth or FWHM ($\Delta\lambda$) and the edge width ($\delta\lambda$). It is assumed that the transmittance curves of adjacent filter bands cross over at the wavelengths where the transmittance is half the maximum value, i.e. at $\lambda \pm \frac{1}{2}\Delta\lambda$. A BBP photometric system is more easily specified by these ‘separation wavelengths’ and the (constant) edge width. The corners of the trapezoid are rounded through convolution with a triangular function of FWHM = 10 nm.

TABLE 1: Relative weight and RMS WFE in each of the 9 considered field points, and for the whole astrometric field (AF). The last two columns give the RMS prediction errors (PE), using a linear regression model, for the filter system in Fig. 2 with 20 nm edge width.

Point No.	Weight	RMS WFE [nm]	PE (stars) [μ as]	PE (quasars) [μ as]
1	4	38.1	1.06	7.87
2	2	42.1	0.95	6.83
3	2	30.5	0.53	2.53
4	2	19.0	0.93	5.05
5	1	12.2	0.87	4.97
6	1	50.1	2.04	16.88
7	2	32.3	0.44	2.21
8	1	28.6	0.84	4.94
9	1	50.0	3.64	27.83
AF	16	35.4	1.32	9.76

2 Method

All calculations were made using current estimates of Gaia-2 parameters (aperture and pixel size, focal length, QE curve [CCD-AF], mirror reflectance [6 reflections in Ag], etc.).

However, since no WFE maps for Gaia-2 are yet available, the ‘old’ maps (Lam50_M2 from 1998) were used, only with the reference radius scaled (in proportion to the along-scan aperture size) from 0.85 m for Gaia-1 to 0.70 m for Gaia-2.

Monochromatic line-spread functions (LSF) were computed as described in GAIA-LL-039, using the scaled WFE maps after removal of piston and tilt terms (proportional to 1, x and y).

Field points 1 through 9 were considered (see SAG-LL-025). The relative weight assigned to each point and its RMS WFE (excluding piston and tilt) are shown in Table 1.

Polychromatic LSF for the AF (no filter) as well as relative photon fluxes in the BBP filter bands were computed for stellar fluxes from the Gunn & Stryker library (175 spectra) plus extinction ($A_V = 0, 2, 4$ mag); in total 525 stellar spectra. The centroid and BBP fluxes were also computed for a set of 101 quasar spectra, obtained by redshifting a standard QSO spectrum by $z = 0, 0.05, \dots, 5.00$.

Centroid positions were computed by cross-correlating with a Gaussian kernel of standard width $s = 1.125$ pixel.

A linear calibration model was assumed, based on stellar data only. That is, a linear regression formula [eq. (6) in GAIA-LL-039] was fitted to the centroid position as function of the BBP fluxes for the stellar data only. The regression formula was then used to *predict* the centroid position for both stars and quasars. The RMS prediction error was computed separately for the stellar and quasar spectra.

3 Results

The run of the centroid position versus wavelength for the monochromatic LSF is shown in Fig. 1. The total variation is typically 0.02–0.05 pixel (1–2 mas) but up to 0.15 pixel (7 mas) for the points with RMS WFE ~ 50 nm.

Figures 2 to 4 show a sequence of filter combinations with varying edge width (Fig. 2), without and with wavelength cut-offs (Fig. 3), and with a smaller number of bands (Fig. 4). The corresponding RMS prediction errors (weighted field averages computed separately for stellar and quasar spectra, as in Table 1) are given in Table 2.

4 Discussion and conclusions

For fixed separation wavelengths (as in Fig. 2) the RMS prediction error clearly decreases with increasing edge width. However, the decrease is rather insignificant until the edge width becomes comparable with the bandwidth, i.e., when the passbands become approximately triangular. This confirms the previous finding that triangular shapes are good for chromaticity calibration, especially for emission-line objects.

The RMS prediction errors in Table 2 are field averages. They should therefore be multiplied by a coefficient of improvement to give the corresponding contribution to the final astrometric accuracies. For the parallax and a five-year effective observation time, the coefficient of improvement is 0.212. For bright stars we may allow an RMS contribution to the parallax of $1 \mu\text{as}$ (cf. GAIA-LL-048), which corresponds to a field-averaged RMS prediction error of $4.7 \mu\text{as}$. All the filters (even with only two passbands) satisfy this requirement for stars with normal spectra. However, for the quasar spectra the RMS prediction error exceeds the limit. This should however not be a problem for the definition of the reference frame, since most of the contributing quasars are faint (18–19 mag) with a vastly greater photon-statistical noise.

For bright stars with peculiar (e.g., emission-line) spectra the prediction error may be a problem except if the edge width is large (< 100 nm). However, it is likely that a much better prediction can be achieved also in this case by using additional data from the MBP. (The simple shapes of the curves in Fig. 1 suggest that this is possible.) Otherwise we may have to accept a slightly degraded astrometric performance for such stars.

To conclude: for chromaticity, nearly rectangular filter bands are acceptable – it does not matter if the edge width is 10, 20, or 40 nm. The choice of separation wavelengths is more important than the edge width. Removing the blue and red wings of the QE curve degrades the chromaticity correction and should therefore be avoided if possible. Four BBP bands are sufficient.

The sample data in Table 1 also indicate that the linear chromaticity model works very well for RMS WFE up to around 42 nm, but that the prediction error appears to explode when the WFE approaches 50 nm. Such large WFE should therefore be avoided in any part of the field used for astrometry.

FIGURE 1: Centroid position as function of wavelength for the monochromatic LSF at the nine points of the AF considered (the curves for the points with the largest WFE, Nos. 6 and 9, are indicated).

TABLE 2: RMS chromaticity prediction error (PE) for the various filter combinations shown in Figs. 2–4.

Figure	Edge width [nm]	PE (stars) [μ as]	PE (quasars) [μ as]
2a	10	1.34	10.02
2b	20	1.32	9.76
2c	40	1.28	8.97
2d	80	1.16	6.96
2e	160	0.74	2.78
3a	20	0.86	7.41
3b	20	1.27	10.05
4a	20	2.81	7.54
4b	20	4.34	12.35

FIGURE 2: Filter profiles with edge width 10, 20, 40, 80 and 160 nm. The separation wavelengths are 500, 650 and 850 nm. The dashed curve is the AF response (QE for CCD-AF and 6 Ag mirrors).

FIGURE 3: Alternative BBP systems with separation wavelengths 550, 700 and 850 nm (edge width = 20 nm). Left (A) without; right (B) with cut-offs at the blue/red end (460 and 920 nm).

FIGURE 4: Alternative BBP systems with three (left, A) and two (right, B) bands (edge width = 20 nm).